

CLIMATE CHANGE AND POST-COVID-19 EFFECTS IN SUDAN: REVIEW OF POLICIES AND INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK

Ibrahim A. Onour
and
Islam M. Mahmoud

CLIMATE CHANGE AND POST-COVID-19 EFFECTS IN SUDAN: REVIEW OF POLICIES AND INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK

Ibrahim A. Onour
and
Islam M. Mahmoud

www.cdpp.co.in

Climate Change and Post-COVID-19 Effects in Sudan: Review of Policies and Institutional Framework

Ibrahim A. Onour¹ and Islam M. Mahmoud²

Abstract

This paper aims to overview policies and institutional frameworks related to climate change issues in Sudan and highlight the main barriers hindering effective climate change management in the country. Investigation of environmental policy issues in the country indicates challenges facing effective implementation of climate change policies, including weakness in the implementation of adaptation strategies and environmental management plans. Due to a shortage of qualified staff in environmental policy issues, there is no assessment of the environmental and socio-economic impacts of climate change. Another barrier is poor capacity, both institutional and individual, at the national and state levels, which would require sustained strengthening to realise the benefits of the NAPA process. The lack of capacities at the institutional level, coupled with poor allocation of resources by the government to address mitigation measures and adaptation actions, puts the implementation of effective climate change policies at risk. Additional barriers include finance for adaptation and mitigation measures, proper awareness, and improper institutional arrangements and policies. Technological research and knowledge-sharing is also a key barrier that is usually linked to a lack of funds, especially funds related to climate change and health issues, which could be addressed through the integration of health into other sectors of the economy. Other barriers identified are staff retention in the health services sector and the imbalance in skills mix in the states. In addition, service conditions, including wages, are not attractive to retain healthcare professionals in health facilities across the country, especially in remote locations. The paper also highlights the post-COVID-19-pandemic effect on different sectors of Sudan's economy for the coming few years.

Keywords: Climate change, Sudan, Policy issues; Post-COVID-19

1 Ibrahim A. Onour, School of Management Studies, University of Khartoum, Sudan
onour@uofk.edu

2 Islam Mohamad Mahmoud, Assistant Professor, School of Management Studies, University of Khartoum

Introduction

Since Sudan is a semi-desert country, it is highly vulnerable to climate change due to the country's dependence on rain-fed agricultural food crops and livestock production for income and employment. The increasing dependence of Sudanese communities on environmentally vulnerable natural resources for survival has created conflict and competition between farmers and pastoralists over scarce resources. In the past few decades, Sudan adopted several climate change assessment programmes to better understand the range of adaptation opportunities that are available, such as the assessments for the National Action Plan for Adaptation (NAPA, 2007, 2014). These efforts aimed to help clarify some strategies for building adaptive resilience to future climatic changes. An examination of Sudan's ecological zones reveals that a large part of its land is vulnerable to changes in temperature and precipitation. In Sudan's agro-pastoral economy, changes in temperature and rainfall variability cause a high risk to food security. The country's inherent vulnerability to rainfall pattern changes can be ascertained by the fact that food security in Sudan is mainly determined by rainfall shortage, particularly in rural areas, where more than 80 per cent of the total population live. The NAPA has developed a programme to identify hotspots that are more vulnerable to rainfall shortages to identify priorities for adaptation (NAPA, 2014). Climate change is expected to cause greater health risks to Sudanese people due to the frequency and magnitude of extreme weather events, such as more heat waves of longer duration, floods, droughts, and sandstorm surges (Figure 1), which cause poor air quality and has an impact on drinking and recreational water quality, as well as causing food-borne diseases (IndexMundi, 2016).

Sudan's Second National Communication (SNC, 2013) indicated that air temperatures had been progressively increasing over the period 1960–2009, with temperature increases between 0.2 °C and 0.4 °C per decade for the periods—March–June and June–September. This implies that, on average, temperatures in 2000–2009 are approximately between 0.8° C and 1.6° C warmer than they were in the 1960–1969 period. Rainfall is also becoming increasingly unpredictable and has significantly decreased in the period 1981–2012 compared to the period 1971–2000.

The most likely climatic risks in Sudan are droughts, floods, and dust storms (Figure 1). Heat waves are rare except in the Red Sea state where they offer frequently (Table 1). In the past three decades, there has been large-scale human suffering in the form of forced out-migration from rural to urban areas due to climatic shocks. Rain-fed farmers and pastoralists are the most affected by these shocks that lead to the disintegration of their communities and disruption in their lifestyles. An initial step in the NAPA consultation process

was to categorise communities or sub-regions within each of the five ecological zones indicated in Table 1. This would help identify the most vulnerable communities to climatic shocks, preserve agricultural production potential, inhibit the spread of disease and conserve water resources (NAPA, 2007).

Figure I: Dust Storm in Sudan

Source: <https://earthobservatory.nasa.gov/NaturalHazards/view.php?id=81127>

Table I: Climate Change Variability and Its Impact on Regions in Sudan

Event	Occurrence	Vulnerable sectors	Sector	Impact
Drought	Frequent	North and Western Sudan (North Kordofan and Darfur), Kassala State and some parts of the rain-fed areas in central Sudan.	Agriculture, livestock, water resources and health.	Loss of crops and livestock (food shortage), decline in the hydroelectric power, displacement wildfire.
Floods	Frequent	Areas within the River Nile basin and low areas from extreme South to far North; Mountain areas along the Red Sea	Agriculture, livestock, water resources and health	Loss of life, crops, livestock, insects and plant diseases, epidemic /vector diseases, a decline in hydro power; damage to infrastructure and settlement areas.

Table 1 Continued

Event	Occurrence	Vulnerable sectors	Sector	Impact
Dust storms	Frequent	Central and northern parts of Sudan	Agriculture, livestock, water resources and health	Air and land traffic accidents and health
Thunderstorms	Infrequent	Rain-fed areas throughout all Sudan	Aviation	Loss of lives and properties.
Heat waves	Rare	Northern, central parts of Sudan besides the Red Sea State.	Health, agriculture and livestock	Loss of lives, livestock and crops
Windstorms	Rare	Central and north-central Sudan	Settlements and service infrastructure	Loss of lives, property, damage to infrastructure (electricity and telephone lines).

Source: NAPA (2007)

The effects of climate change on agricultural productivity have been tackled in many papers, among them, Deryng et al. (2016), Alam (2013), Kimball et al. (2002), Adams et al. (1998), Adams et al. (1995), Lobell and Field (2008), Lang (2007), Schlenker et al. (2006), Derner et al. (2003), Tubiello and Ewert (2003), and Fischer et al. (2002), and Onour (2019). Deryng et al. (2016) and Alam (2013) indicated that increased CO₂ concentrations in the atmosphere may reduce the utilisation of water in crops and significantly alleviate yield losses due to climate change; however, Alam (2013), Onour (2019), and Adams et al., (1998) state that the increasing CO₂ concentrations may cause a decline in agricultural productivity and “will act as a fuel to the higher prices of goods and services in the economy”. Blanc (2011) and Lobell and Field (2008) show that CO₂ concentration has significant long-run and short-run effects on millet yield but not on cassava and maize yields; it also has an insignificant impact on sorghum yields.

The following sections of the paper include a discussion on environmental policy analysis and institutional and regulatory issues related to climate change. The final section concludes the study.

Policy Analysis

Sudan has taken strong actions and displayed political will to minimise the risks generated by climate change to its natural resources and economy. It has done this by specifying and implementing adaptation measures while engaging in low-carbon development strategies to stimulate its national economy sustainably, even though Sudan has a voluntary general obligation for adopting a low-carbon development approach.

As a result, the Sudan government ratified the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change UNFCCC in 1993 and the Kyoto Protocol in 2005 (TNA, 2013). In response to its commitment to the UNFCCC, the Sudan government prepared several national documents, including the Initial/first National Communication (INC). Sudan's INC identified water resources, agriculture, and public health as most vulnerable to climate variability risks. In an attempt to update the INC, a Second National Communication (SNC) was prepared and submitted to the UNFCCC in 2013. The SNC (2013) designated Sudan's coastal zones as increasingly vulnerable and urged for these zones to be taken into account in climate change adaptation policies. Furthermore, in 2015, Sudan submitted its Intended Nationally Determined Contribution (INDC) for COP21. Currently, it is preparing its Third National Communication (TNC) programme. All these processes have led to the belief that effective adaptation to climate change will be critical for protecting the country's most vulnerable populations and maintaining long-term sustainable national development programmes. Concerted efforts in this direction are evidenced by Sudan's completion of Sudan's National Adaptation Plan (NAP) and its implementation of a series of pilot adaptation initiatives in rural communities. These pilot initiatives are aimed to survey the technical and socio-economic viability of specific adaptation plans while putting in place a conducive environment for implementing NDC.

Sudan's NAP aims to integrate the risks of climate change into all national development plans and reduce vulnerability by building resilience and adaptive capacity. As such, Sudan's NAP programme entails vulnerability assessment and adaptation in all states of Sudan by covering essential development sectors, such as agriculture, water, health and coastal zones.

Sudan conducted its Technology Needs Assessment (TNA) for adaption and mitigation in 2013, which covers industry, forestry and energy, in addition to two priority sectors, namely agriculture and water. In line with this, Sudan aims to adopt sectoral measures to engage in low-carbon development, guided by the long-term national development strategies, policies and plans, which are stated in the strategic plan document for 2007–2033. Furthermore, Sudan has also prepared a proposal for a low-carbon development strategy, but its implementation is pending owing to its dependence on international climate funding.

Regulatory Framework on Climate Change

The Interim Constitution of Sudan has a provision under Chapter II, article 19, stating that the State of Sudan shall “promote public health and guarantee equal access and free primary health care to all citizens”. Furthermore, Article 11 of the Interim Constitution also states:

1. The people of Sudan shall have the right to a clean and diverse environment; the State and the citizens have the duty to preserve and promote the country’s biodiversity.
2. The State shall not pursue any policy, or take or permit any action, which may adversely affect the existence of any species of animal or vegetative life, their natural or adopted habitat.
3. The State shall promote, through legislation, sustainable utilization of natural resources and best practices with respect to their management.

Sudan was among the first African countries to propagate legislation concerning the management and protection of the environment. It did so since the early years of the 20th century. Magzoub (1998) indicated that there were about 150 orders, acts and related regulations addressing environmental issues in Sudan. However, these regulations and acts were confronted early on by challenges of legislative and institutional dualism at national, state-level and local levels, as well as between the three levels of governance. These hindrances have prevented Sudan from building a consistent and socially acceptable system of environmental legislation. Accordingly, the current institutional setup needs to be enhanced with a more clearly specified climate change policy, as there are still major threats to climate change in Sudan due to the discontinuity of external funding corresponding to the UNFCCC obligations.

Institutional Framework

A key feature in the environmental governance structure in Sudan is the diversity of small units linked to environmental authority but not directly linked to each other. Key federal-level environmental institutions in Sudan include the Ministry of Environment, Higher Council for Environment and Natural Resources (HCENR), and Forestry and Physical Development (MEFPD). Other important institutions at the federal level include the Ministry of Agriculture, Ministry of Tourism and Wildlife, Desertification Control and Coordination Unit of the Ministry of Agriculture, Ministry of Industry, and Ministry of Water Resources and Electricity.

The HCENR was established in 1992 as a government agency with a mandate to coordinate governmental efforts for resolving climate change-related

issues as well as organise national policies and legislation for conservation and environmental protection. It has also the task of liaising with stakeholders in international agreements related to environment and climate change risk exposure. The organisation is required to manage the relationship between various government agencies and national and state governments in their efforts towards environment conservation and natural resource management.

The Ministry of Environment and Physical Development

The Ministry of Environment and Physical Development (MEPD) was established in 2003 with a mandate stated in the Environment Act of 2001, with the Higher Council for Environment and Natural Resource (HCENR). Its mandate, which is stated in the Environment Act of 2001, includes urban planning, surveying and construction. However, the MEPD is ill-equipped in terms of human resources. The Department of Environmental Affairs is located within the MEPD and has only 10 staff members.

Sudan's Higher Council for Environment and Natural Resources

The Higher Council for Environment and Natural Resources (HCENR) was established in 1992 to coordinate government efforts for sustainable development. It is the central institution for creating climate change instruments, including the NAP. The HCENR carries out its operations through a secretariat and is headed by a secretary-general. Almost all HCENR activities are funded by donors because government allocations are not enough to carry out significant work.

The Ministry of Environment was established in 1995, three years after the HCENR was founded. In 2006, the membership of the HCENR was expanded to twenty-six ministries, two representatives of universities and a representative for environmental NGOs. The revised task of the HCENR, as stated in the 2001 Environmental Act, includes the following:

1. Coordinate efforts on natural resource management among concerned government bodies and between the federal and state governments;
2. Set up long-term plans for environmental protection and sustainable use of natural resources;
3. Undertake an intermittent review of environmental legislation to make them effective tools for sustainable development;
4. Support research on environmental and natural resource management; and
5. Raise environmental consciousness and education.

With responsibilities that include both coordination and implementation activities, the HCENR is playing the role of the lead national agency in the management of climate change issues in the country. The HCENR also plays an important role in encouraging state governments to set up State Environmental Councils (SECs). Guided by HCENR guidelines, these SECs have the responsibility of protecting the environment at the state and local levels. At present, only five SECs are operational in North Darfur, Sinnar, Gedarif, River Nile and Khartoum states. Although these institutions are currently operating at low profile levels, their effectiveness can be increased through capacity-building efforts and increased funding. One of the main areas of interest at the state level is setting up adaptation-focused planning institutions in each of Sudan's eighteen states. Inter-agency technical teams with experts from related government agencies and research institutions have been established in each state. The capacities of these units have been boosted by intensive training workshops and the establishment of networks to aid in the exchange of experience and knowledge.

Table 2: Evaluation of Sudan's Higher Council of Environment and Natural Resources

Institution Strength	Weakness	Threat	Opportunity	
Higher Council of Environment and Natural Resources	Climate change coordination unit in place.	Enforcement of environmental policies/laws is weak.	Coordination is a must for mobilising climate financing	Resources available from donors and UN agencies for climate change activities
	In charge of coordinating climate resilience work.	Lengthy environmental impact assessment approval process.	Ministry of Environment has control over the HCENR and the appointment of the minister is political.	Two communications centres have been developed and the NAP is in place.
	Focal point for climate financing	Low allocation of resources by the government for environment-management related activities	Lack of financial assessment for climate change	Lifting US sanctions would make it easier to mobilise funding for climate change

Table 2 Continued

Institution	Strength	Weakness	Threat	Opportunity
Higher Council of Environment and Natural Resources	Mainstreaming adaptation and mitigation of climate change issues into development plans.	Inadequate resources at local-level environment offices.	Incomplete guidelines for community-based interventions.	The Ministry of Finance is developing guidelines for Public-Private Partnerships (PPP) that may entice the private sector to invest in renewable energy.

Source: Sudan National Adaptation Plan (2016)

Ministry of Energy and Mining

The General Administration for Environment and Safety is one of the administrative bodies of the Ministry of Energy and Mining. These bodies have the following mandates:

1. setting policies and strategies of environmental plans;
2. overseeing the application of environmental laws by commercial energy companies;
3. establishing an energy information system; and
4. assisting in environmental awareness.

Major weaknesses of the administration include understaffing and the low technical capacity of the existing staff, which hinder its effectiveness in carrying out its mandate.

Ministry of Water Resources and Electricity

The objectives and responsibilities of the Ministry of Water Resources and Electricity include:

- setting strategies and plans related to national water resource policies;
- assessing Sudan's need for water resources and their efficient utilisation;
- utilising Sudan's share of Nile waters and developing cooperation between the Nile basin countries;
- exploring and managing non-Nile water resources;
- assessing and monitoring ground water basins; and
- mitigating and controlling the effects of floods by using hydraulic structures and flood-forecasting techniques.

Ministry of Health

The Ministry of Health (MOH) aims to provide quality health services that meet the needs of the people in the country. This objective can be attained by placing health at the centre of the country's development policy and ensuring efficient utilisation of resources.

Established in 1995, the National Health Insurance Fund (NHIF) is a mandatory scheme that covers a third of the Sudanese population (11.8 million beneficiaries), mainly from the formal employed sector. The NHIF covers the medical insurance needs of its members through a national insurance fund that is partially funded by its members and partially by the state. Members are categorised into contributory and non-contributory. The NHIF, headquartered in Khartoum, has branches in all states. Since the central government has devolved its power to individual states, the NHIF's characteristics and quality of operations greatly vary from state to state. Though the NHIF covers over thirty-seven per cent of the population in the country, it only funds four per cent of the country's total health expenditure. As such, the level of benefits provided and the quality of services offered as well as the funding for the scheme is open to question.

Table 3: Other Relevant Institutions for Climate Change

No.	Name of Ministry / Institution
1	Federal Ministry of Health
2	Higher Council for Environment and Natural Resources, Ministry of Environment
3	Ministry of Electricity, Irrigation and Water Resources
4	Sudan Farmers Union
5	Ministry of Foreign Affairs
6	Sudanese Environmental Conservation Society
7	National Council for Strategic Planning
8	Ministry of International Cooperation
9	Sudanese Metrological Authority
10	Ministry of Agriculture
11	Faculty of Agriculture, University of Khartoum
12	Ministry of Science and Technology
13	Faculty of Forestry University of Khartoum
14	Institute of Environmental Studies, University of Khartoum
15	Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning

Sudan Meteorological Authority

The Sudan Meteorological Authority (SMA) has a mandate from the Government of Sudan to observe all the meteorological activities in the country. No other institution is allowed to carry out such activities without the approval of the SMA. The function of SMA is to provide meteorological information and services for the conservation of the natural environment, which will ensure the safety of society, growth of the economy, and poverty alleviation through sustainable development of the economy. Currently, the SMA is working very hard through self-financed projects and technical assistance to enhance its observation network (Figure 2) to support key stations installed across the country. Furthermore, it will also help revive the silent stations in selected states of the NAPA project and the climate risk finance project for sustainable and climate-resilient rain-fed farming and pastoral systems. The mandate of the SMA mandate is to avail weather information and forecast for policy issues supporting small farmers and pastoralists as end-users.

Figure 2: Meteorological Stations in Sudan

Source: Sudan Metrological Agency

Post-COVID-19 Effect

Sudan recorded its first COVID-19 case on 15 March 2020, and at the beginning of August, the Federal Ministry of Health confirmed that nearly 15,000 people had contracted the virus, including the 800 + who had already died from the disease across the country. Despite the efforts of the government and local organisations to raise awareness of the risks associated with COVID-19 and methods to prevent its transmission, key practices like social/physical distancing have not been adhered to by the public. Instead, denial, misinformation, stigma, and rumour-mongering emerged as added challenges to the COVID-19 response, preventing positive health-seeking behaviour in the affected populations.

The COVID-19 pandemic has emerged against a backdrop of increasing humanitarian needs as communities grapple with multiple and simultaneous shocks. The ongoing economic crisis, years of internal political conflicts, recurring droughts and floods, and disease outbreaks continue to lead to displacement, high levels of food insecurity, and malnutrition that affect the lives and livelihoods of many Sudanese people. The necessary COVID-19 containment measures adopted by the Ministry of Health further exacerbated the economic crisis as Sudan's health system was already under extreme stress before the pandemic.

The FAO (2021) estimates that COVID-19 in Sudan and related containment measures are adversely impacting all four dimensions of food security: availability, access, utilisation and stability. Availability is affected due to labour shortage in the farms plus shortage due to lack/increased cost of transportation of items. Access to food is challenged as many micro-enterprises and small informal businesses have been restricted or curtailed, causing loss of income among affected populations. With limited access of food, poor families will increasingly resort to low quality and lesser quantity of food, which will, in turn, cause undernutrition. Sudan's Food Security Technical Secretariat (FSTS) already projected that consumption patterns would shift towards low-quality food, which will increase malnutrition. Restrictions and interruptions in the flow of goods and services are expected to have a significant impact on the food security situation in the country in the coming two years. As a result, families in rural areas are also expected to resort to livelihood-based coping strategies, including the sale of productive assets or animals, thus depleting their assets. According to WFP, a majority of households have already spent more than 75 per cent of their expenditure on food, limiting their ability to create or invest in livelihood assets. Safely managed water, sanitation, and hygiene services are an essential part of slowing the spread of COVID-19 in Sudan, but this too is being challenged by limited resources and accessibility. According to the Joint Monitoring

Programme for Water Supply, Sanitation and Hygiene, only 20 per cent of people in Sudan have regular access to basic hygiene services—soap and clean water.

The poor and vulnerable, especially the urban poor, whose income and livelihoods depend mainly on informal economic activities and daily wages are already struggling to feed their families. This is expected to further deteriorate with the implementation of the necessary COVID-19 restrictions. Moreover, domestic trade disruptions are expected to create unstable food market prices, as already seen in the price increase of basic goods in major urban centres.

The agriculture sector will be negatively impacted too; fuel scarcity and increased transportation costs exacerbated by containment measures have already led to a price rise in food and agricultural inputs. Transportation blockages or interruptions will disrupt the distribution of inputs like animal feed. Some farmers may encounter shortages in labour and farming inputs and experience difficulties in deliveries, which might also affect domestic and regional supply chains.

In summary, the COVID-19 pandemic has had an unprecedented social and economic impact on Sudan, including increased prices of basic foods, rising unemployment, and falling exports (Figure 3). The crisis has also highlighted the importance of safe water, sanitation,

and hygiene practices, which remain inadequate. The outbreak is anticipated to further challenge the country's public health preparedness and response systems and adversely impact the economy.

Figure 3: COVID-19 Pandemic Impact

Concluding Remarks

Based on Sudan's regulatory and institutional approach to climate change issues, it is possible to deduce the following main barriers to effective adaptation action in the country.

Climate change directives and policies are not well incorporated into the national policy and planning systems. This is mainly because of the weaknesses and limitations of the national management systems of climate

change response and data processing in the country. Moreover, there have been limited efforts to raise awareness and understanding of climate change risks. As government institutions related to climate change are vulnerable to political instability in the country, policies and strategies related to environmental issues do not effectively incorporate Multilateral Environment Agreements such as those of the UNFCCC.

Another barrier is poor capacity, both institutional and individual, at the national and state levels, which would require sustained strengthening before it can benefit from the NAPA process. Both the NCSA (2016) report as well as the NAPA (2016) delineate the capacity gaps that exist at the institutional level at the HCENR, the agency that oversees climate change adaptation and mitigation efforts. The instruments, documents and studies that were developed under the auspices of the HCENR were funded by different donors, including the UN. Capacities to formulate these different documents were outsourced to individual national and international experts either directly or through funded projects. In these projects, the role of the HCENR is usually supervisory or logistical. However, the head of the Climate Change Unit within the HCENR is the key technical staff who participates in the discussions related to the formulation of projects and other relevant activities. Lack of capacity at the institutional level, coupled with poor resource allocation by the government to address mitigation measures and adaptation actions, makes the HCENR entirely dependent on donor assistance to address obligations, requirements and projects implemented by the Ministry of Environment.

On the other hand, at the local level, government-related climate change mitigation and adaptation measures are entrusted to line ministries that vary from one state to another. In some cases, the line ministry may be the State Ministry of Environment, in others, it may be the Ministry of Agriculture or some other relevant ministry. The staff in charge of activities related to climate change discharge their functions mostly through committees formed by the ministry or through ad hoc committees formed through the projects at the central level. All this work is guided through the HCENR. The capacities of these staff are modest, and they usually receive training or orientation to carry out the assignments directed through the relevant projects or the state ministry, usually through central guidance by the HCENR.

Shortage of funds, both at the national and international levels, has hindered the implementation of key measures identified in the Sudan NAPA. A majority of the people in the country are affected by extreme poverty and poor health conditions, making them more vulnerable to climate change.

Additional barriers include finance for adaptation and mitigation measures, proper awareness, improper institutional arrangements, and policies.

Technological research and knowledge sharing is also a key barrier that is usually linked to a lack of funds, especially funds related to climate change and health issues, which could be addressed by integrating health into other sectors of the economy. Some other barriers that can be identified include staff retention in the health services sector and the imbalance in skills mix in the states. In addition, service conditions, including wages, are not attractive to retain health care professionals in health facilities across the country, especially in remote locations.

References

- Adams, J. M. (2007). *Vegetation–climate interaction: How vegetation makes the global environment*. Springer Praxis Books. Springer-Verlag Berlin, Heidelberg.
- Alam, M. Q., (2013). Climate change, agricultural productivity, and economic growth in India: The bounds test analysis. *International Journal of Applied Research and Studies*, 2(11), 1–14.
- Adams, R. M., Fleming, R. A., Chang, C. C., McCarl, B. A., & Rosenzweig, C. (1995). A reassessment of the economic effects of global climate change on US agriculture. *Climate Change*, 30, 147–167.
- Adams, R. M., Hurd, B. H., Lenhart, S., & Leary, N. (1998). Effects of global climate change on agriculture: An interpretative review. *Climate Research*, 11, 19–30.
- Derner, J. D., Johnson, H. B., Kimball, B. A., Pinter Jr, P. J., Polley H. W., et al. (2003). Above- and below-ground responses of C3–C4 species mixtures to elevated CO₂ and soil water availability. *Global Change Biology*, 9, 452–460.
- Deryng, D., Elliott, J., Folberth, C., Müller, M., Pugh, T. A. M., et al. (2016). Regional disparities in the beneficial effects of rising CO₂ concentrations on crop water productivity. *Nature Climate Change*, 6, 786–790. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2995>
- FAO Report. (2021). *The Sudan: Agricultural livelihoods and food security in the context of COVID-19*. <http://www.fao.org/emergencies/resources/documents/resources-detail/en/c/1371755/>
- Fischer, G., Van Velthuisen, H. T., Shah, M. M., & Nachtergaele, F. O. (2002). *Global agro-ecological assessment for agriculture in the 21st century: methodology and results*.

- Fischer, G., Shah, M., van Velthuisen, H., & Nachtergaele, F. (2001). Global agro-ecological assessment for agriculture in the 21st century: Methodology and results. International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis Laxenberg, Austria. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations: Rome, Italy.
- Higher Council for Environment and Natural Resources (HCENR). Sudan's National Climate Change Policies and Measures Final Report, October 2015. http://postconflict.unep.ch/publications/UNEP_Sudan_env_gov_review.pdf
- INC. 2003. Sudan's Initial National Communication. Ministry of Environment, Forestry and Physical Development Higher Council for Environment and Natural Resources (HCENR), Khartoum.
- IndexMundi (2016). Sudan: Environmental and Climate Change Assessment. Prepared for IFAD's Country Strategic Opportunities Programme 2013–2017 and Sudan National Adaptation Plan, July 2016. http://www.indexmundi.com/sudan/major_infectious_diseases.html
- Kimball, B. A., Kobayashi, K., & Bindi, M. (2002). Responses of agricultural crops to free-air CO₂ enrichment. *Advances in Agronomy*, 77, 293–368.
- Lang, G. (2007). Where are Germany's grains from Kyoto? Estimating the effects of global warming on agriculture. *Climate Change*, 84(3–4), 423–439.
- Lobell, D. B., & Field, C. B. (2008). Estimation of the carbon dioxide (CO₂) fertilization effect using growth rate anomalies of CO₂ and crop yields since 1961. *Global Change Biology*, 14, 39–45.
- NAP. 2016. Sudan, (2016). National Adaption Plan, Republic of the Sudan, Ministry of Environment, Natural Resources& Physical Development Higher Council for Environment and Natural Resources. Khartoum.
- NAPA. 2007. National Adaptation Programme of Action. Republic of the Sudan, Ministry of Environment and Physical Development, Higher Council for Environment and Natural Resources, Khartoum.
- NCSA. 2008, National Capacity Self-Assessment for Global Environmental Management, Republic of Sudan, Ministry of Environment and Physical Development, Higher Council for Environment and Natural Resources. Khartoum.

- Onour, I. A., (2019). Effect of carbon dioxide concentration on cereal yield in Sudan. *Management and Economics Research Journal*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.18639/MERJ.2019.740622>
- Pugh, T. A. M., Müller, C., Elliott, J., Deryng, D., Folberth, C., Olin, S., & Arneth, A. (2016). Climate analogues suggest limited potential for intensification of production on current croplands under climate change. *Nature communications*, 7(1), 1-8.
- Ruane, A. C., Major, D. C., Winston, H. Y., Alam, M., Hussain, S. G., Khan, A. S., ... & Rosenzweig, C. (2013). Multi-factor impact analysis of agricultural production in Bangladesh with climate change. *Global environmental change*, 23(1), 338-350.
- Report on Meeting with the Higher Council of Environment and Natural Resources, Mr. Nagmeldin Goutbi Elhassan, Climate Change Expert and Former Assistant Project Manager of the NAP, HCENR, Sudan, Wednesday 9 August 2017. http://postconflict.unep.ch/publications/UNEP_Sudan_env_gov_review.pdf
- SNC. 2013. Sudan's Second National Communication under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, Ministry of Environment, Forestry & Physical Development, Higher Council for Environment and Natural Resources. Khartoum.
- Schlenker, W., Hanamann, W., & Fisher, A. (2006). The impact of global warming on US agriculture: An econometric analysis of optimal growing conditions. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 88(1), 113–125.
- Sudan National Adaptation Programme of Action, UNDP. <https://www.adaptation-undp.org/projects/sudan-national-adaptation-programme-action-napa>
- TNA. 2013. Technology Need Assessment for Developing Countries for Climate Change, Republic of Sudan, Higher Council for Environment and Natural Resources. Khartoum.
- UN Environment Programme. Sudan post-conflict environmental assessment report, 8 February 2007. <https://www.unenvironment.org/resources/assessment/sudan-post-conflict-environmental-assessment>

10-3-303, 3rd Floor, Serene Heights Building,
Humayun Nagar, Masab Tank, Hyderabad - 500 028
info@cdpp.co.in | www.cdpp.co.in